

Unveiling variability and associations between yield and nutritional quality traits in Pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum* (L.) R. Br.)

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Abstract

Micronutrient deficiency poses a significant global health challenge, affecting more than two billion individuals, with a pronounced impact on women, children, and infants, especially in developing nations. Implementing agricultural strategies, such as incorporating micronutrient-rich crop-based foods and bio-fortified crop varieties containing elevated levels of iron (Fe) and zinc (Zn), emerges as a cost-effective and sustainable solution. To address this issue, a field experiment was conducted during the summer season of 2023, aiming to evaluate the association of Fe and Zn contents with yield-related traits. The trial revealed a high genetic coefficient of variation (GCV) and phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV). The yield related traits such as panicle length, panicle girth, single earhead weight, single earhead grain weight, test weight and leaf breadth showed highly significant association with grain yield. A positive and highly significant correlation coefficient ($r = 0.522$, $p < 0.01$) between Fe and Zn content and Fe and grain yield was observed, suggesting the potential for simultaneous improvement of both micronutrients without affecting grain yield.

Key words : Pearl millet genotypes, variability, correlation, path analysis

Introduction

The global health challenge of micronutrient deficiency, particularly in developing nations, has been extensively documented. Over two billion individuals worldwide, especially children and women of reproductive age, experienced the insufficient intake of iron (Fe) and zinc (Zn), from which iron deficiency being a leading cause of anemia (Boncompagni *et al.*, 2018). This issue is most pronounced in resource-limited regions, especially among communities heavily dependent on staple cereals for their energy and nutritional requirements. Various approaches have been suggested to address micronutrient malnutrition, including medical supplementation, industrial fortification of food, dietary diversification, and crop biofortification, which involves developing crop varieties with

elevated micronutrient levels (Wakeels *et al.*, 2018). Biofortification holds significant importance for populations who were reliant on agriculture, providing a cost-effective and sustainable strategy that prioritizes those most vulnerable to deficiencies (Finkelstein *et al.*, 2017).

Pearl millet, a vital coarse grain cereal and forage crop grown in arid and semi-arid regions of the Indian subcontinent and Africa, plays a crucial role in ensuring dietary energy and nutritional security (Srivastava *et al.*, 2020). Known for its resilience to drought conditions, pearl millet thrives in marginal areas where other major cereals often struggle to yield substantial crops (Kumawat *et al.*, 2019). Pearl millet has a significant contribution to cereal consumption in specific regions of India, serving as an economical source of grain iron (Fe) and zinc (Zn). Many of the studies have confirmed the effectiveness of iron-biofortified pearl millet in improving iron status, especially in children. Hence there is a need to alter the micronutrient composition for the benefit of end-users by exploring the presence of variation for grain Fe and Zn content among different pearl millet varieties,. Understanding the association between yield, yield attributes, and the interrelation between yield and nutritional quality traits is crucial for simultaneous improvement of crop for grain yield and nutritional traits. The current investigation is concentrated on identifying micronutrient-dense pearl millet parental lines, marking a critical step in the development of micronutrient biofortified pearl millet hybrids or composites.

Materials and Methods

The experimental materials consisted of 103 lines, including B lines, R lines, and land races, obtained from the Department of Millets at TNAU, Coimbatore. A field trial was conducted during the summer season of 2023 at the Millets Breeding Station, Department of Millets, TNAU, Coimbatore, utilizing a randomized block design (RBD) with two replications. Each entry was planted in two rows, each measuring 4 meters in length, with an intra-row spacing of 15 cm and an inter-row spacing of 50 cm. The entire crop period, all recommended agronomic practices were followed. Soil Fe and Zn levels were evaluated by DTPA extractable method (Lindsay and Norwell, 1978) at the time of planting, revealing soil Fe ranging from 7.2 to 11.4 mg/kg and Zn ranging from 0.8 to 2.1 mg/kg. Grain samples from each entry, harvested at physiological maturity, underwent analysis for Fe and Zn contents using Energy Dispersive X-rays Fluorescence (ED-XRF) at TRRI, Aduthurai. Analysis of variance for the randomized block design was conducted following the method

outlined by Panse and Sukhatame, 1961. Genetic parameters such as PCV and GCV, heritability, and genetic advance as a percentage of mean were categorized using the methods given by Burton (1951), Lush (1940), and Johnson *et al.*, 1955 respectively. All the statistical analysis were done by OPSTAT online statistical software package (developed by Sheoran *et al.*, 1998)

Results and discussion

Variability studies for yield and nutritional quality traits

The analysis of variance (**Table 1**) revealed the existence of variation among 103 pearl millet genotypes for all 16 morphometric and nutritional quality traits under study (Annamalai *et al.*, 2020; Anuradha *et al.*, 2020). The examination of mean values and various genetic variability parameters such as genotypic coefficient of variance, phenotypic coefficient of variance, heritability, genetic advance, and genetic advance mean for different traits (**Table 2**) indicated the significant variations for most of the studied traits and it could be utilized to develop hybrid varieties with simultaneous improvement in grain yield and other yield-contributing traits (Rajpoot *et al.*, 2023).

As per Deshmukh *et al.* (1986), genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV%) and phenotypic coefficient of variance (PCV%) values exceeding 20% are classified as high, values below 10% are considered as low, and those falling between 10% and 20% are medium. For all the traits investigated, higher Phenotypic Coefficient of Variation (PCV) than Genotypic Coefficient of Variation (GCV) was observed (Table 2; Fig 1), indicating the influence of the environment on the observed traits. Higher estimates of PCV than GCV also been reported in pearl millet by Basavaraj *et al.*, 2017; Annamalai *et al.*, 2020. Notably, leaf sheath length, panicle length, single earhead weight, single earhead grain weight, thousand grain weight, and single plant yield exhibited higher PCV and GCV, suggesting significant variability among pearl millet genotypes for these traits. These results were similar to the earlier findings by Annamalai *et al.*, 2020 for grain yield, seed weight per spike and 1000 grain weight and by Choudhary *et al.*, 2012 and Rajpoot *et al.*, 2023 for number of productive tillers per plant, 1000grain weight and grain yield, by Anuradha *et al.*, 2018, Kumawat *et al.*, 2019 and Ram *et al.*, 2014 for number of productive tillers per plant and grain yield. These high variability estimates indicated the presence of more variation in the population for the studied traits for further selection and crop improvement.

The heritability of traits provides insights into the effectiveness of selection concerning inheritance. However, combining heritability with genetic advance as a percentage of mean (GAM) offers a more dependable estimate of selection. For all the traits, except days to 50 percent flowering, days to maturity, and the number of productive tillers, high heritability (broad sense) and high genetic advance as a percentage of mean were observed (Table 2). These results were similar to the earlier findings by Annamalai *et al.*, 2020 for grain yield, plant height and number of nodes per plant, by Rajpoot *et al.*, 2023 for plant height, numbers of productive tillers per plant, panicle length, panicle diameter, test weight, and yield per plant, by Anuradha *et al.*, 2020 for thousand grain weight, by Dadarwal *et al.*, 2020 for days to 50% flowering, plant height, panicle length, panicle girth, thousand-seed weight, and single plant yield. These findings suggested that the direct selection strategies could effectively enhance these specific traits.

Association studies for yield and nutritional quality traits

The selection of superior genotypes based on seed yield as such may not be effective (Bikash *et al.*, 2013). Correlation of distinct traits provides the knowledge on being inherited together from one generation to next. It helps in indirect selection for the complex trait like yield through selection by other biometrical traits which are closely and positively associated (Anuradha *et al.*, 2018). This association is due to pleiotropic gene action or linkage or more likely both (Dapke *et al.*, 2014).

Correlations between yield components and quality components were examined, and the resulting phenotypic (r_p) and genotypic (r_g) correlation coefficients are presented in Table 3 (Fig 2). The genotypic correlation coefficient was more than the phenotypic correlation coefficient for the characters studied (Dhedhi *et al.*, 2016 and Rasitha *et al.*, 2019) which inferred the existence of considerable inherent association among the traits (Naveen *et al.*, 2016). Single plant yield exhibited highly significant positive correlations with the traits leaf breadth, panicle length, panicle girth, single earhead weight, single earhead grain weight, thousand grain weight, and grain Fe content. These findings supported with the results reported by Annamalai *et al.*, 2020, Rasitha *et al.*, 2019 and Singh *et al.*, 2014 for test weight. These results inferred the selection of these traits would lead to simultaneous improvement in seed yield per plant. Grain Fe content exhibited a positive correlation with grain yield per plant, suggesting the potential for improving both grain yield and Fe content simultaneously. This study concludes that selecting for high grain yield and Fe content can be achieved

without adversely affecting grain yield. In contrast, Chakraborti *et al.* (2010) reported a significant negative correlation between Fe content and grain yield in maize.

The current investigation emphasizes a substantial and positive correlation between iron (Fe) and zinc (Zn) content, indicating the potential for concurrent selection of these traits to enhance nutritional quality (Table 3). Earlier studies on pearl millet by Velu *et al.* (2008), Govindaraj *et al.* (2009), Gupta *et al.* (2009), Anuradha *et al.* (2018), on maize by Long *et al.* (2004) and on sorghum by Reddy *et al.* (2010) and Ashok Kumar *et al.* (2009) have consistently revealed the significant and positive correlations between Fe and Zn contents. These findings strongly suggest the simultaneous selection for increased levels of both Fe and Zn contents.

Although a non-significant negative correlation was identified between grain Zn content and grain yield, a similar lack of correlation between Zn content and grain yield was noted in a previous study on pearl millet conducted by Gupta *et al.*, 2009. Comparable negative correlations between Zn and grain yield have been observed in other cereals, such as sorghum (Reddy *et al.*, 2005; Ashok Kumar *et al.*, 2009), wheat (Morgounov *et al.*, 2007) and Maize (Chakraborti *et al.* 2009). No correlations were observed between grain Zn content and other yield-related traits except for Fe content in the present study. Whereas grain Fe content exhibited associations with days to 50% flowering, days to maturity, leaf breadth, panicle girth, and single earhead grain weight. These findings suggest the potential for genetic enhancement of both Fe and Zn contents in pearl millet without compromising on grain yield, seed weight, or earliness.

Estimation of correlation alone may not be sufficient due to mutual cancellation of component traits, so it is necessary to study the path co-efficient analysis, which takes into account, the cause of relationship in addition to the degree of relationship (Dapke *et al.*, 2014). The trait single earhead grain weight showed high positive direct effect on grain yield per plant and thousand grain weight and Grain Fe showed moderate positive direct effect on grain yield per plant. This revealed the true relationship of these characters with seed yield per plant. Hence, direct selection for these traits could be rewarding for the improvement of seed yield in pearl millet.

Single earhead grain weight showed highly positive indirect effect on grain yield per plant via earhead weight and panicle girth. Path analysis revealed that for increasing the seed yield per plant, direct selection of genotypes with high panicle weight was found to be of

useful. These traits were important as component traits for formulation of selection index in future (Kalagare *et al.*, 2022).

Conclusion

The current study revealed significant variation in all 16 agronomic and nutritional quality traits across the 103 pearl millet genotypes examined. Notably, high Genetic Coefficient of Variation (GCV) and Phenotypic Coefficient of Variation (PCV) were observed for Leaf Sheath Length (LSL), Panicle Length (PL), Single Earhead Weight (SEW), Single Earhead Grain Weight (SEGW), Thousand Grain Weight (TGW), and Single Plant Yield (SPY), indicating substantial variability within the population. Among all the traits studied, the greatest variability was observed in Single Earhead Weight and Single Earhead Grain Yield.

Grain yield exhibited a strong association with Single Earhead Grain Yield, Single Earhead Weight, Panicle Girth, and Thousand Grain Weight, which infers that these traits predominantly influenced by additive gene action. Consequently, selecting for grain yield through these traits is considered to be more effective. Additionally, there was a high correlation between Grain Fe content and Grain Zn content, suggesting the possibility of improving both the micronutrient contents simultaneously. Also grain Fe exhibited positive association with grain yield which infers the without compromising the grain yield both the micronutrient contents could be improved.

References

- Annamalai, R., Aananthi, N., Arumugam Pillai, M. and Leninraja, D. 2020. Assessment of variability and character association in pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum* (L.) R. Br.). International. Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences. 9(6): 3247-3259.
- Anuradha, N., Kranthi Priya, P., Patro, T. S. S. K., Sandhya Rani, Y. and Triveni, U. 2020. Character association, variability and heritability studies for grain yield and its yield attributes in pearl millet (*Pennisetum Glaucum* (L.) R. Br). International Journal of Chemical Studies. 11:1459-1464.
- Anuradha, N., Satyavathi, C. T., Bharadwaj, C., Sankar, M., Singh, S. P. and Pathy, T. L. 2018. Pearl millet genetic variability for grain yield and micronutrients in the arid zone of India. Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry, 7(1): 875-878.

- Ashok Kumar, A., Reddy, B. V., Ramaiah, B., Sanjana Reddy, P., Sahrawat, K. L. and Upadhyaya, H. D. 2009. Genetic variability and plant character association of grain Fe and Zn in selected core collection accessions of sorghum germplasm and breeding lines. *Journal of SAT Agricultural Research*, 7: 1-4.
- Basavaraj, P. S., Biradar, B. D. and Sajjanar, G. M. 2017. Genetic variability studies for quantitative traits of restorer (R) Lines in Pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum* (L.) R. Br.). *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, 6(8): 3353-3358.
- Bikash, A., Yadav, I. S. and Arya, R. K. 2013. Studies on variability, correlation and path analysis in pearl millet. *Forage Research*, 39(3): 134-139.
- Boncompagni, E., Orozco-Arroyo, G., Cominelli, E., Gangashetty, P. I., Grando, S., Kwaku Zu, T. T., Daminati, M.G., Nielsen, E. and Sparvoli, F. 2018. Antinutritional factors in pearl millet grains: Phytate and goitrogens content variability and molecular characterization of genes involved in their pathways. *PloS one*, 13(6), e0198394.
- Burton, G. W. 1951. Quantitative inheritance in pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) 1. *Agronomy Journal* 43 (9):409-417.
- Chakraborti, M., Prasanna, B. M., Singh, A. M. and Hossain, F. 2010. Generation mean analysis of kernel iron and zinc concentrations in maize (*Zea mays*). *The Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 80(11).
- Choudhary, R., Jat, B., Anwale, R., Dhikwal, S. and Sharma, K. 2012. Studies on estimates of genetic variability and character association of yield components and protein content in pearl millet. *Forage Res.*, 38: 80-85.
- Dadarwal, S. L., Rajput, S. S. and Yadav, G. L. 2020. Studies on genetic variability parameters in maintainer lines of pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum* (L.) R. Br.). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 9(6): 795-797.
- Dapke, J. S., Shah, D. S., Pawar, G. N., Dhembre, V. M. and Kumar, M. 2014. Genetic variability and character association over environment in pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum* (L.) R. Br.) under dryland conditions of Gujarat. *The Bioscan*, 9(2): 863-867.

- Deshmukh, S. N., Basu, M. S. and Reddy, P. S. 1986. Genetic variability, character association and path coefficients of quantitative traits in Virginia bunch varieties of groundnut. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences* 56:816-821(812).
- Dhedhi, K. K., Ansodariya, V. V., Chaudhari, N. N., Sanghani, J. M. and Sorathiya, J. S. 2016. Genetic variability and correlation coefficient for fodder yield and its components in forage pearl millet hybrids under rainfed conditions of Gujarat. *International Journal of Bio-resource and Stress Management*, 7: 970-977.
- Finkelstein, J. L., Haas, J. D. and Mehta, S. 2017. Iron-biofortified staple food crops for improving iron status: a review of the current evidence. *Current opinion in biotechnology*, 44: 138-145.
- Govindaraj, M., Rai, K. N., Kanatti, A., Upadhyaya, H. D., Shivade, H. and Rao, A. S. 2020. Exploring the genetic variability and diversity of pearl millet core collection germplasm for grain nutritional traits improvement. *Scientific Reports*, 10(1): 21177.
- Govindaraj, M., Selvi, B. and Rajarathinam, S. 2009. Correlation studies for grain yield components and nutritional quality traits in pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum* (L.) R. Br.) germplasm. *World Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 5(6): 686-689.
- Gupta, S. K., Velu, G., Rai, K. N. and Sumalini, K. 2009. Association of grain iron and zinc content with grain yield and other traits in pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum* (L.) R. Br.). *Crop Improvement*, 36(2): 4-7.
- Johnson, H.W., Robinson, H.F. and Comstock, R. E. 1955. Estimates of genetic and environmental variability in soybeans 1. *Agronomy Journal* 47 (7): 314-318.
- Kalagare, V. S., Ganesan, N. M., Iyanar, K., Chitdeshwari, T. and Chandrasekhar, C. N. 2022. Multivariate analysis in parental lines and land races of pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum* (L.) R. Br.). *Electronic Journal of Plant Breeding*, 13(1): 155-167.
- Kumawat, K. R., Sharma, N. K. and Sharma, N. 2019. Genetic variability and character association analysis in pearl millet single cross hybrids under dry conditions of Rajasthan. *Electronic Journal of Plant Breeding*, 10(3): 1067-1070.

- Lindsay, W. L., and Norvell, W. 1978. Development of a DTPA soil test for zinc, iron, manganese, and copper. *Soil science society of America journal*, 42(3): 421-428.
- Long, J. K., Bänziger, M. and Smith, M. E. 2004. Diallel analysis of grain iron and zinc density in southern African-adapted maize inbreds. *Crop Science*, 44(6): 2019-2026.
- Lush, J.L. 1940. Intrasine correlation and regression of offspring on dams as a model of estimating heritability of character. *Proceedings of the American society for Animal production*. 33:293-301.
- Morgounov, A., Gómez-Becerra, H. F., Abugalieva, A., Dzhunusova, M., Yessimbekova, M., Muminjanov, H., Zelenskiy, Y., Ozturk, L. and Cakmak, I. 2007. Iron and zinc grain density in common wheat grown in Central Asia. *Euphytica*, 155: 193-203.
- Naveen, R., Sumathi, P. and Manivannan, N. 2016. Trait association among beta carotene content and yield attributes in recombinant inbred lines of pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum* (L.) R. Br.). *Agricultural Science Digest-A Research Journal*. 36(3): 202-206.
- Panse, V. G., and Sukhatme, P. V. 1961. *Statistical Methods for Agricultural Workers*. Indian Council of Agricultural Research.
- Ram, M., Singh, S. P., Singh, P. K., Singh, A. and Parveen, S. 2014. Genetic variability analysis for yield and yield contributing traits in pearl-millet (*Pennisetum glaucum* L.). *Trends in Biosciences*. 7(17): 2491-2495.
- Rajpoot, P., Tripathi, M. K., Solanki, R. S., Tiwari, S., Tripathi, N., Chauhan, S., Pandya, R.K. and Khandelwal, V. 2023. Genetic variability and multivariate analysis in pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum* (L.) R. Br.) germplasm lines. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 12(4): 216-226.
- Rasitha, R., Iyanar, K., Ravikesavan, R. and Senthil, N. 2019. Studies on genetic parameters, correlation and path analysis for yield attributes in the maintainer and restorer lines of pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*(L.) R. Br). *Electronic Journal of Plant Breeding*, 10(2): 382-388.
- Reddy, B.V.S., Ramesh, S., and Longvah, T. 2005. Prospects of breeding for micronutrients and β -carotene dense sorghums. *Int Sorghum Millets News letter*. 46:10–14.

- Reddy, P. S., Reddy, B. V., Kumar, A. A., Ramesh, S., Sahrawat, K. L. and Rao, P. V. 2010. Association of grain Fe and Zn contents with agronomic traits in sorghum. *Indian Journal of Plant Genetic Resources*. 23(3): 280-284.
- Sheoran, O.P; Tonk, D.S; Kaushik, L.S; Hasija, R.C and Pannu, R.S (1998). *Statistical Software Package for Agricultural Research Workers*. Department of Mathematics Statistics, CCS HAU, Hisar (139-143).
- Singh, B., Upadhyay, P. K. and Sharma, K. C. 2014. Genetic variability, correlation and path analysis in pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum* (L.) R. Br.). *Indian Research Journal of Genetic and Biotechnology*. 6: 491-500.
- Srivastava, R. K., Singh, R. B., Pujarula, V. L., Bollam, S., Pusuluri, M., Chellapilla, T. S., Yadav, R. S. and Gupta, R. 2020. Genome-wide association studies and genomic selection in pearl millet: Advances and prospects. *Frontiers in Genetics*, 10:1389.
- Velu, G., Rai, K. N. and Sahrawat, K. L. 2008. Variability for grain iron and zinc content in a diverse range of pearl millet populations. *Journal of Crop Improvement*, 35(2): 186-191.
- Wakeel, A., Farooq, M., Bashir, K., & Ozturk, L. 2018. Micronutrient malnutrition and biofortification: recent advances and future perspectives. *Plant micronutrient use efficiency*, 225-243.

Table 1. Analysis of variance for 16 yield components and nutritional quality traits in pearl millet genotypes

Sources of variation	Df	Mean sum squares															
		DFF	DM	PH	LSL	LL	LB	NOPT	NON	PL	PG	SEW	SEGW	TGW	FE	ZN	SPY
Genotypes	102	23.97**	17.29**	1681.13**	19.53**	145.81**	0.76*	0.418**	2.79**	46.16**	4.28**	282.79**	114.91**	15.93**	286.79**	77.15**	463.28**
Error	102	0.66	0.74	77.26	0.08	7.69	0.21	0.12	0.08	4.82	0.17	7.67	2.72	0.37	7.22	3.15	36.89

*, ** represents significant at 5% and 1% level

Table 2. Genetic parameters for 16 yield components and nutritional quality traits in pearl millet genotypes

Character	DFF	DM	PH	LSL	LL	LB	NOPT	NON	PL	PG	SEW	SEGW	TGW	FE	ZN	SPY
Mean	48.83	80.82	153.39	12.22	55.65	4.07	4.15	6.37	22.34	8.61	35.62	25.76	10.25	64.14	45.75	74.67
GCV	6.99	3.56	18.46	22.83	14.93	13.03	9.56	18.27	20.35	16.67	32.93	29.07	22.79	18.36	13.29	19.55
PCV	7.19	3.71	19.33	23.36	15.74	17.04	12.27	18.82	22.60	17.31	33.83	29.76	22.93	18.82	13.85	21.78
h^2 (Broad sense)	94.64	91.8	91.21	95.46	89.97	58.43	60.72	94.25	81.11	92.80	94.72	95.38	98.78	95.08	92.15	85.25
GAM	14.01	7.03	36.32	45.94	29.17	20.51	15.35	36.54	37.76	33.09	66.02	58.49	46.68	36.87	26.29	37.19

Table 3. Genotypic and phenotypic Correlation coefficients for yield components and nutritional quality traits in pearl millet genotypes

Character	DFF	DM	PH	LSL	LL	LB	NOPT	NON	PL	PG	SEW	SEGW	TGW	Fe	Zn	SPY
DFF		0.713**	-0.371**	-0.170*	0.119	0.234**	-0.365**	-0.282**	0.047	0.228**	0.182**	0.241**	0.008	0.350**	0.017	0.115
DM	0.777**		-0.335**	-0.124	0.227**	0.136	-0.248**	-0.108	-0.008	0.069	0.135	0.151*	0.008	0.196**	0.019	0.018
PH	-0.386**	-0.383**		0.381**	0.013	-0.008	0.147*	0.532**	0.144*	-0.126	0.064	0.021	0.006	-0.111	-0.005	0.111
LSL	-0.183**	-0.123	0.409**		0.119	0.138*	0.135	0.304**	0.169*	0.012	0.281**	0.186**	0.197**	-0.195**	-0.061	0.167*
LL	0.123 ^{NS}	0.254**	0.020	0.146*		0.251**	-0.031	0.140*	0.291**	0.079	0.138*	0.136	0.039	0.044	-0.052	0.102
LB	0.298**	0.197**	-0.019	0.198**	0.362**		-0.192**	-0.032	0.277**	0.352**	0.328**	0.306**	0.206**	0.229**	-0.009	0.279**
NOPT	-0.443**	-0.357**	0.211**	0.170*	-0.063	-0.353**		0.131	-0.157*	-0.364**	-0.136	-0.213**	-0.086	-0.212**	-0.035	-0.251**
NON	-0.298**	-0.119	0.566**	0.321**	0.145*	-0.007	0.205**		0.025	-0.093	0.056	0.093	-0.038	0.005	-0.000	0.149*
PL	0.048	-0.000	0.166*	0.189**	0.329**	0.366**	-0.141*	0.034		0.305**	0.326**	0.354**	0.210**	0.096	0.031	0.181**
PG	0.245**	0.066	-0.136	0.018	0.078	0.474**	-0.481**	-0.102	0.339**		0.445**	0.486**	0.328**	0.288**	-0.064	0.405**
SEW	0.190**	0.144*	0.082	0.304**	0.146*	0.411**	-0.165*	0.051	0.347**	0.467**		0.866**	0.290**	0.054	-0.123	0.469**
SEGW	0.261**	0.154*	0.025	0.200**	0.162*	0.408**	-0.276**	0.096	0.388**	0.514**	0.909**		0.285**	0.182**	-0.054	0.554**
TGW	0.008	0.010	0.005	0.200**	0.043	0.289**	-0.105	-0.042	0.232**	0.347**	0.302**	0.291**		0.046	-0.106	0.359**
Fe	0.364**	0.205**	-0.110	-0.207**	0.035	0.332**	-0.286**	0.008	0.102	0.304**	0.066	0.198**	0.047		0.490**	0.205**
Zn	0.010	0.036	0.002	-0.067	-0.057	0.025	-0.024	0.001	0.044	-0.072	-0.125	-0.068	-0.114	0.522**		-0.101
SPY	0.132	0.002	0.106	0.179*	0.134	0.377**	-0.298**	0.148*	0.219**	0.455**	0.520**	0.613**	0.389**	0.222**	-0.101	

*, ** represents significant at 5% and 1% level

Where DFF –Days to50% flowering, DM – Days to maturity, PH – Plant Height, LSL – Leaf Sheath Length, LL – Leaf Length, LB - Leaf Breadth , NOT – No of Productive Tillers, NON – No of Nodes, PL – Panicle Length, PG – Panicle girth, SEW – Single earhead weight, SEGW – Single earhead grain weight, TGW – Thousand Grain Weight, Fe – Grain Fe content, Zn – Grain Zn content, SPY – Single Plant Yield; Upper and lower diagonal values represents phenotypic and genotypic correlations.

Table 4. Path analysis for 16 yield components and nutritional quality traits in pearl millet genotypes

Traits	DFE	DM	PH	LSL	LL	LB	NOT	NN	PL	PG	SEW	SEGW	TGW	FE	ZN	SPY
DFE	0.0647	-0.1430	-0.0255	-0.0086	0.0085	0.0150	0.0643	-0.0239	-0.0059	0.0138	-0.0341	0.1633	0.0017	0.0428	-0.0010	0.1318
DM	0.0503	-0.1840	-0.0253	-0.0058	0.0175	0.0099	0.0517	-0.0096	0.0001	0.0037	-0.0259	0.0964	0.0021	0.0240	-0.0036	0.0016
PH	-0.0250	0.0705	0.0660	0.0192	0.0014	-0.0009	-0.0307	0.0453	-0.0207	-0.0076	-0.0148	0.0156	0.0010	-0.0129	-0.0002	0.1061
LSL	-0.0118	0.0225	0.0270	0.0470	0.0100	0.0099	-0.0247	0.0257	-0.0235	0.0010	-0.0548	0.1252	0.0432	-0.0243	0.0067	0.1791
LL	0.0080	-0.0467	0.0013	0.0068	0.0688	0.0181	0.0091	0.0116	-0.0411	0.0044	-0.0264	0.1010	0.0092	0.0041	0.0057	0.1340
LB	0.0193	-0.0363	-0.0012	0.0093	0.0249	0.0501	0.0513	-0.0006	-0.0457	0.0266	-0.0741	0.2547	0.0625	0.0390	-0.0025	0.3773
NOT	-0.0287	0.0656	0.0140	0.0080	-0.0043	-0.0177	-0.1450	0.0164	0.0176	-0.0270	0.0298	-0.1723	-0.0227	-0.0336	0.0024	-0.2976
NN	-0.0193	0.0219	0.0374	0.0151	0.0100	-0.0004	-0.0297	0.0800	-0.0042	-0.0057	-0.0092	0.0602	-0.0092	0.0009	-0.0001	0.1477
PL	0.0031	0.0001	0.0110	0.0089	0.0227	0.0184	0.0205	0.0027	-0.1247	0.0190	-0.0624	0.2425	0.0501	0.0120	-0.0044	0.2193
PG	0.0159	-0.0121	-0.0090	0.0008	0.0053	0.0237	0.0697	-0.0082	-0.0423	0.0562	-0.0842	0.3210	0.0750	0.0357	0.0072	0.4548
SEW	0.0123	-0.0264	0.0054	0.0143	0.0101	0.0206	0.0240	0.0041	-0.0432	0.0263	-0.1801	0.5676	0.0652	0.0078	0.0125	0.5203
SEGW	0.0169	-0.0284	0.0017	0.0094	0.0111	0.0204	0.0400	0.0077	-0.0484	0.0289	-0.1637	0.6246	0.0629	0.0233	0.0068	0.6132
TGW	0.0005	-0.0018	0.0003	0.0094	0.0029	0.0145	0.0152	-0.0034	-0.0289	0.0195	-0.0544	0.1819	0.2162	0.0056	0.0114	0.3888
FE	0.0236	-0.0377	-0.0072	-0.0097	0.0024	0.0167	0.0415	0.0006	-0.0128	0.0171	-0.0120	0.1240	0.0102	0.1174	-0.0522	0.2219
ZN	0.0007	-0.0066	0.0001	-0.0032	-0.0039	0.0012	0.0034	0.0001	-0.0055	-0.0040	0.0225	-0.0422	-0.0247	0.0613	-0.0999	-0.1006

Where DFE –Days to50% flowering, DM – Days to maturity, PH – Plant Height, LSL – Leaf Sheath Length, LL – Leaf Length, LB - Leaf Breadth , NOT – No of Productive Tillers, NN – No of Nodes, PL – Panicle Length, PG – Panicle girth, SEW – Single earhead weight, SEGW – Single earhead grain weight, TGW – Thousand Grain Weight, Fe – Grain Fe content, Zn – Grain Zn content, SPY – Single Plant Yield

Fig 1. Mean performance and GCV and PCV of 16 yield and nutritional quality traits

Fig 2. Correlogram for 16 yield and nutritional quality traits in pearl millet genotypes

